

Table 2. Calculation of the number of tablespoons of liquid insecticides to add to your sprayer each sprayerload to achieve a dosage of 0.75 kg active ingredient/ha. IIRI.

Sprayerloads (no./ha) ^a	Number of tablespoons per sprayerload of liquid insecticides when insecticide concentration (% a.i.) on the bottle is											
	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70
10	50	38	30	25	21	19	17	15	14	13	12	11
15	33	25	20	17	14	13	11	10	9	8	8	7
20	25	19	15	13	11	9	8	8	7	6	6	5
25	20	15	12	10	9	8	7	6	5	5	5	4
30	17	13	10	8	7	6	6	5	5	4	4	4
35	14	11	9	7	6	5	5	4	4	4	3	3
40	13	9	8	6	5	5	4	4	3	3	3	3
45	11	8	7	6	5	4	4	3	3	3	3	2
50	10	8	6	5	4	4	3	3	3	3	2	2
55	9	7	5	5	4	3	3	3	2	2	2	2
60	8	6	5	4	4	3	3	3	2	2	2	2
65	8	6	5	4	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2
70	7	5	4	4	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2

^aFrom Table 1.

Table 3. Calculation of the number of tablespoons of wettable powders to add to your sprayer each sprayerload to achieve a dosage of 0.75 kg a.i./ha. IIRI.^a

Sprayerloads (no./ha)	Number of tablespoons of WP per sprayerload				
	Etrofolan Mipcin Hytoc MIPC 50 WP	Shellcarb BPMC 40 WP	Tsumacide MTMC 50 WP	Orthene 75 SP	Sevin Tercyl 85 WP
10	39	51	37	34	38
15	26	34	24	23	25
20	20	25	18	17	19
25	16	20	15	14	15
30	13	17	12	11	13
35	11	14	10	10	11
40	10	13	9	9	9
45	9	11	8	8	8
50	8	10	7	7	8
55	7	9	7	6	7
60	7	8	6	6	6
65	6	8	6	5	6
70	6	7	5	5	5
G/tablespoon	3.8	3.7	4.1	2.9	2.3

^aWP = wettable powder, SP = soluble powder.

column labeled 50 down to the row designated 35 sprayerloads/ha (33 rounds off to 35). The correct dosage then is 4 tablespoons/sprayerload. Note that a tablespoon = 10 ml.

Table 3 gives calculations for wettable powders. Wettable powders are calculated individually because the weight of one tablespoon of the formulated product varies among insecticides. For liquids we assumed that the weight of 1 liter of insecticide was equal to the weight of 1 liter of water. But wettable powders have different dispersing agents and carriers that have

different weights. If a recommended wettable powder insecticide is not in Table 3, use the following formula for 0.75 kg. a.i./ha dosage to calculate the appropriate data in tablespoons for 10-70 sprayerloads/ha:

$$\text{No. of tablespoons} = 750 \times \frac{100}{\text{concentration of product}} \times \frac{1}{\text{sprayerloads (no./ha)}} \times \frac{1}{\text{g/l tablespoon (10 cc) of product}}$$

Note that you need to know the weight of 1 tablespoon of the formulated product.

Observations on a “blue form” of green leafhopper

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In January 1980 a few colored insects, resembling green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* were noticed in the insect maintenance cages at AICRIP headquarters, Hyderabad. Twenty-five such insects, both males and females, were caged on TN1 seedlings. Eight days later the first-instar nymphs appeared and molted within 2-3 days. After that the second-instar nymphs were clearly distinguishable from those of “normal” green leafhopper nymphs. Later generations showed that the blue forms bred true and that the blue and green forms can crossbreed. To determine if the two forms differ in the ability to transmit tungro virus disease, males and females of both forms were released on tungro-infected TN1 plants for 24 hours. Transmission tests showed that as transmitters of rice tungro virus the blue females were as efficient as the green, but the green males were better than the blue. Further work is in progress and the insects have been sent to the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology for identification. ■

The “knockdown speed” of insecticides against brown planthopper and green leafhopper

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The “knockdown action” of some commonly used pesticides for the control of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Dist.) was studied.

Single hills (5 plants each) of 25-day-old rice plants were transplanted in plastic pots (3 inches in diameter). Desired concentrations of insecticides were sprayed on the potted plants on a

turntable at 25 ml/pot at 5 days after transplanting. Each treatment was replicated twice. The sprayed plants were allowed to dry for 1 hour. Twenty brachypterous BPH females in the 1st experiment and 20 5th-instar GLH nymphs in the 2d, were caged on treated plants with a glass tube covered with muslin. The exposure periods were 1, 2, 4, and 6 hours for BPH and 0.5, 1, 2, and 3 hours for GLH. Mortality was recorded after the exposure periods. Moribund insects were treated as dead. For mortality in the control, the corrected percentage of mortality in the treatment was calculated by Abbott's

LT₅₀ and LT₉₀ values of pesticides against the brown planthopper and green leafhopper. Bhopal, M.P., India.

Pesticide	Conc (% active ingredient)	Values (h)			
		Brown planthopper		Green leafhopper	
		LT ₅₀	LT ₉₀	LT ₅₀	LT ₉₀
Control	0	—	—	—	—
Methyl parathion	0.025	3.5	5.0	1.6	2.0
Quinalphos	0.025	2.4	5.0	1.5	2.2
Phosphamidon	0.025	2.6	4.0	1.5	2.4
Carbaryl	0.05	2.0	3.0	1.25	1.8
BPMC	0.05	< 1.0	1.0	0.8	1.1
BPMC + carbaryl (1:1)	0.05	1.1	1.8	0.6	0.9
Landrin	0.05	2.0	3.0	1.5	2.5

formula and plotted on log-probit paper against time in hours; graphical Lethal Time (LT₅₀) and Lethal Time 90 (LT₉₀)

were calculated for the different insecticides (see table). ■

Leaf folder control through interference in chitin biosynthesis

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The effect on larvae of the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* Guenee of a new insecticide Dimilin (R)—with a unique mode of action on insects was studied. Dimilin (diflubenzuron) interferes with chitin biosynthesis and deposition in the insect cuticle. Interference in chitin deposition in the insect exoskeleton leads to inhibition of molting.

Potted TN1 rice plants were sprayed with 200 ppm Dimilin with a hand atomizer. When the spray fluid dried up, final-instar larvae of the leaf folder were released on plants confined in cylindrical

Morphogenetic changes in leaf folder larvae that fed on Dimilin®-treated rice leaves. A: normal pupae; B: pupae with deformed proboscis; C & D: larval-pupal mosaics. Tamil Nadu, India.

polyester cages. The larvae which fed on Dimilin-treated plants formed silken webs, but were unable to molt and develop into pupae (see figure). The insecticide caused deformities: pupae with deformed proboscis and larval-pupal mosaics. The pupal deformities are evidently due to interference in chitin

deposition. In all the 5 replications of 10 larvae each, 80% of the test insects were deformed. The result suggests that Dimilin—a new generation of insecticide—has the potential to control the rice leaf folder through physiological inhibition of chitin deposition. ■

Irrigation and water management

Effect of irrigation regimes on agronomic characters of rice

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The effects of different irrigation regimes on agronomic traits of the semidwarf rice variety Cauvery were studied in a greenhouse trial. Continuous flooding

was the superior irrigation regime in its influence on grain yield and nutrient recovery, but it did not improve the harvest index. Yield and nutrient recovery performance was poor in rice plants grown under continuous saturated conditions. Flooding at the reproductive stage was found to increase yield, nutrient recovery, and harvest index more

than flooding at the vegetative stage.

Nutrient recovery was closely associated with yield but harvest index was an independent trait and differed from yield trends. Harvest index decreased successively in the following order of irrigation regime: I₂, I₁, I₄, I₃ (see table). The highest harvest index in treatment I₂ was probably because of proper equi-